

HALOGENATION. PART XX. HALOGENATION OF FLUORENE.

BY PHILDEO SAHAY VARMA and V. SUBBA RAO.

The following halogen compounds of fluorene have been prepared and the position of the halogen atoms with the exception of one or two definitely established :—2-bromo-7-chlorofluorene, 2-chloro-7-iodofluorene, 2-iodo-7-chlorofluorene, 2-bromo-7-iodofluorene, 2-iodo-7-bromofluorene, 2:7-dibromo-6 (?) -iodofluorene, 2:7-dichloro-6 (?) -bromofluorene, & 2:7-diiodofluorene.

From the study of the literature, it appears that simple halogen derivatives alone of fluorene have been obtained before. Of the chloro derivatives of fluorene, mono-, di-, tri-, and penta-chloro derivatives have been prepared by the direct action of chlorine under different conditions. By the action of bromine under the varying conditions of the experiments, similar bromo derivatives have been obtained. Of the iodo derivatives, only two mono-iodo derivatives, 2-iodo-, and 9-iodofluorene have been prepared (Chanussot, *Anal. Assoc. Quim. Argentina*, 1927, **28**, 5 ; Wanschmidt, *Ber.*, 1926, **59**, 2092). No attempt has been made before for the preparation of mixed halogen derivatives of fluorene. The authors have attempted to prepare such compounds as a result of which the following mixed halogen compounds have now been obtained. 2-chloro-7-bromofluorene, 2-bromo-7-chlorofluorene, 2-chloro-7-iodofluorene, 2-iodo-7-chlorofluorene, 2-bromo-7-iodofluorene, 2-iodo-7-bromofluorene, 2:7-dibromo-6(?) -iodofluorene, 2:7-dichloro-6(?) -bromofluorene.

Most of the above compounds have been obtained by more than one method so that it has been possible to ascertain with certainty the position of the halogen atoms in the fluorene molecule. For example, 2-chloro-7-bromofluorene has been prepared by brominating 2-chlorofluorene and also by replacing the amino group in 2-chloro-7-aminofluorene by bromine.

In addition to the above compounds 2:7-diiodofluorene has been prepared for the first time by the direct iodination of fluorene in glacial acetic acid at 100° using a mixture of concentrated nitric acid and fuming sulphuric acid and also by replacing the amino group or groups in 2:7-

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diaminofluorene or in 2-iodo-7-aminofluorene by iodine. Hence the positions of the iodine atoms in the molecule of this compound could be known with certainty.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

2-Chloro-7-bromofluorene. (i) *From 2-Chlorofluorene.*—2-Chlorofluorene (5 g.), prepared by the direct action of chlorine on fluorene in benzene at 80°-90° in presence of iodine (Buffle, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1932, 15, 1483), was dissolved in chloroform (30 c.c.) and iron (0.5 g.) was introduced as a halogen carrier. Keeping the temperature of the solution below 10°, liquid bromine (1.5 c.c.) was added drop by drop in 25 minutes. The resulting product was gently warmed on a water-bath to drive out the hydrogen bromide, filtered from iron and allowed to stand for an hour for crystallisation. The solid separating was recrystallised twice from carbon disulphide when colourless, transparent, monoclinic crystals were obtained, m. p. 157°, yield 3.4 g. It is very soluble in carbon disulphide and chloroform, and sparingly in benzene and alcohol. (Found : Total halogen, 40.84. $C_{13}H_9ClBr$ requires Total halogen, 41.32 per cent).

(ii) *From 2-Chloro-7-aminofluorene.*—A solution of 2-chloro-7-aminofluorene (5 g.), prepared by nitrating 2-chlorofluorene and reducing the chloronitro compound (Courtot and Vignati, *Compt. rend.*, 1927, 184, 1779), was diazotized by sodium nitrite (2 g.) solution in 5% aqueous hydrochloric acid at 5°, in the usual manner. This mixture was slowly added to cuprous bromide (3.5 g.) dissolved in hydrobromic acid (50 c.c.) and shaken, when a greenish yellow product separated out. The product was allowed to stand overnight, filtered, washed with water and then crystallised from glacial acetic acid as colourless crystals, m. p. 157°, yield 2.9 g. It is identical with the compound obtained in the preceding experiment.

2-Bromo-7-chlorofluorene. (i) *From 2-Bromofluorene.*—Through a solution of 2-bromofluorene (Hodkinson and Mathews, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1883, 43, 163) in chloroform (25 c.c.), a current of dry chlorine was passed in the presence of iodine (0.5 g.) in diffused day light for an hour. The chloroform was allowed to evaporate and the solid residue washed with aqueous sodium hydroxide (5%) until free from iodine, then with water. It was crystallised twice from glacial acetic acid as transparent needles, m.p. 156-57°, yield 3.7 g. It is soluble in acetone, carbon tetrachloride and carbon disulphide. (Found : Total halogen, 40.56. $C_{13}H_9ClBr$ requires Total halogen, 41.32 per cent).

(ii) *From 2-Bromo-7-aminofluorene.*—2-Bromo-7-aminofluorene (5g.) (Courtot and Vignati, *loc. cit.*) was dissolved in 5% hydrochloric acid and diazotised with sodium nitrite (1.8 g.) in the usual manner. Copper powder (2 g.) was added and the mixture allowed to stand for about 20 hours in cold water. The product was extracted with benzene, washed with water, dried over calcium chloride and allowed to stand and the solid separating was crystallised from carbon disulphide, m.p. 155.5°, yield 0.7 g. The properties agree with the compound prepared by the preceding method.

2-Chloro-7-iodofluorene. (i) *From 2-Chlorofluorene.*—A mixture of concentrated nitric acid (3 c.c.) and fuming sulphuric acid (2 c.c.) was added in drops to 2-chlorofluorene, (5 g.) iodine (4.5 g.) and glacial acetic acid (25 c.c.) in about 20 minutes and the whole refluxed for about 3½ hours on a water-bath. The solution was cooled, poured into water and the solid separating extracted with benzene, the benzene extract washed with aqueous sodium hydroxide (5%) and then with water, dried over fused calcium chloride, allowed to stand, when crystals separated, yield 4.1 g. On crystallisation from warm acetic acid it melts at 121.5°. It is soluble in carbon tetrachloride, acetone and ether. (Found: Total halogen, 49.13. $C_{13}H_9ClI$ requires Total halogen, 49.77 per cent).

(ii) *From 2-Chloro-7-aminofluorene.*—Diazotised 2-chloro-7-aminofluorene (5 g.) was treated with a solution of potassium iodide (4.9 g.) in water (20 c.c.) at about 8°. The mixture was heated on a water-bath for 1 hour, extracted with benzene. The extract was washed with aqueous sodium hydroxide (5%) and then with water, dried over calcium chloride and allowed to stand when pale yellow crystals separated, m.p. 121-22° after crystallisation from glacial acetic acid, yield 1.9 g. It is soluble in carbon disulphide and chloroform.

2-Iodo-7-chlorofluorene.—2-Iodo-7-nitrofluorene (Chanussot, *loc. cit.*) was reduced with zinc dust and aqueous alcohol (30 c.c. of alcohol and 10 c.c. water) and dissolved in aqueous hydrochloric acid (5 c.c. of *d* 1.17 and 20 c.c. of water) and treated with sodium nitrite (2 g. in 15 c.c. of water) solution below 10°. Cuprous chloride (3 g.), dissolved in dilute hydrochloric acid (25 c.c.), was then carefully added and the mixture allowed to stand for 16 hours. The solid separating was washed with water, extracted with benzene, and the extract allowed to stand. After repeated crystallisation from hot glacial acetic acid pale yellow needles, m.p. 122°, were obtained, yield 2.1 g. It is freely soluble in chloroform and acetone and end moderately in alcohol. (Found: Total halogen, 48.93. $C_{13}H_9ClI$ requires Total halogen, 49.77 per cent).

2-Bromo-7-iodofluorene. (i) *From 2-Bromofluorene.*—A mixture of 2-bromofluorene (5 g.), iodine (3.4 g.) and glacial acetic acid (20 c.c.) was treated with a mixture of fuming sulphuric acid (2 c.c.) and concentrated nitric acid (3 c.c.) and the whole refluxed on a water-bath for 4 hours. The solid obtained on pouring the cold mixture into water was extracted with benzene. The benzene extract was washed with dilute sodium hydroxide (5%) solution, and then with water, dried over calcium chloride and allowed to stand. The solid separating was crystallised from hot acetic acid as yellowish needles, m.p. 162°, yield 3.7 g. It is soluble in benzene and chloroform. (Found: Total halogen, 57.17. $C_{13}H_8BrI$ requires Total halogen, 55.80 per cent).

(ii) *From 2-Bromo-7-aminofluorene.*—2-Bromo-7-aminofluorene (5 g.) was diazotised and treated with potassium iodide (2%) solution and allowed to stand overnight. It was then extracted with carbon tetrachloride and the extract washed with aqueous sodium hydroxide (5%) solution and with water, dried over calcium chloride and allowed to stand. The solid separating was crystallised from glacial acetic acid, m.p. 161–62°, yield 2.2 g. It is found to be identical with the compound obtained by the direct iodination of 2-bromofluorene.

2-Iodo-7-bromofluorene.—2-Iodo-7-aminofluorene (5 g.) was diazotised and treated with cuprous bromide (3.5 g.) in aqueous hydrobromic acid (20 c.c.) and left to stand overnight in the cold. A pale yellow solid separated which was filtered and crystallised in needles from acetic acid, m.p. 160.5°, yield 2.3 g. (Found: Total halogen, 54.31. $C_{13}H_8BrI$ requires Total halogen, 55.80 per cent).

2:7-Dibromo-6(?)iodofluorene.—2:7-Dibromofluorene (5 g.), prepared by the action of bromine on fluorene in carbon disulphide (Fittig and Schmitz, *Annalen*, 1878, 193, 137; Werner and Egger, *Ber.*, 1904, 37, 3029), was heated with iodine (2.6 g.) and glacial acetic acid (20 c.c.) and heated under reflux on a water-bath and a mixture of concentrated nitric acid (3 c.c.) and fuming sulphuric acid (2 c.c.) was added 5 drops at a time, and the heating continued for about 3½ hours. When cooled, the mixture was poured into water, filtered and the solid washed several times with aqueous sodium hydroxide (5%) and finally with water. It was extracted with chloroform, the chloroform extract dried over calcium chloride and left to stand. It was crystallised from acetic acid as yellowish granular particles, m.p. 146.5°, yield 4.1 g. It is soluble in carbon disulphide, acetone and benzene. (Found: Total halogen, 65.27. $C_{13}H_7Br_2I$ requires Total halogen, 63.78 per cent).

2:7-Dichloro-6(?)bromofluorene.—2:7-Dichlorofluorene (5 g.), prepared by passing chlorine through a solution of fluorene in chloroform (Hodkinson

and Mathews, *loc. cit.*) was dissolved in chloroform (25 c. c.) and iron (0.5 g.) was introduced as a halogen carrier. Liquid bromine (2 c. c.) was added drop by drop in course of 20 minutes. Some crystals separated out which were filtered, washed with carbon tetrachloride and filtered free from iron. The carbon tetrachloride extract gave needles, m. p. 143°. yield 3.5 g. It is soluble in acetone, benzene and carbon disulphide. (Found: Total halogen, 46.71. $C_{13}H_7Cl_2Br$ requires Total halogen, 48.08 per cent)

2 : 7-Diiodofluorene. (i) From 2:7-Diaminofluorene.—A solution of 2 : 7-diaminofluorene (Schmidt and Hindever, *Ber.*, 1931, 64, 1793) in dilute hydrochloric acid was diazotised at 5° with sodium nitrite (2 g.) solution and then treated with potassium iodide solution (4 g. in 20 c. c. of water) and allowed to stand overnight. It was extracted with benzene, washed first with aqueous sodium hydroxide, then with water, decolourised by animal charcoal, filtered, dried and allowed to stand. On recrystallisation from glacial acetic acid pale brown needles, m. p. 155.5°, soluble in chloroform, ether, acetone, and warm alcohol, were obtained, yield 2.8 g. (Found : I, 59.85. $C_{13}H_8I_2$ requires I, 60.90 per cent).

(ii) From 2-Iodo-7-aminofluorene.—2-Iodo-7-aminofluorene (5 g.) was diazotised and treated with potassium iodide (2.5 g.) solution and treated as mentioned above, when crystals of diiodofluorene were obtained, yield 2.9 g.

(iii) From Fluorene.—Fluorene (5 g.) iodine (8 g.) and glacial acetic acid (25 c. c.) were heated on a water-bath and a mixture of strong nitric acid (3 c. c.) and fuming sulphuric acid (2 c. c.) was added, a few drops at a time in half an hour, and the whole refluxed for about 4 hours. On cooling, the solution was washed with water, extracted with benzene and the benzene extract washed first with dilute sodium hydroxide solution and then with water. It was dried over calcium chloride and allowed to stand and the crystals were purified by repeated crystallisation from alcohol, yield 1.9 g.

Work on similar lines is in progress.